

NAQSHBANDIYA TARIQATINING O'ZIGA XOS JIHATLARI.

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Annotatsiya. Tasuvvuf o'z vaqtida islom dinining vujudga kelishi va keng tarqalishi mustaxkamlanishi va rivojlanish jarayoni bilan o'zviy bog'langan holda paydo bo'ldi va uzoq taraqqiyot yo'lini bosib o'tdi. Uning ilk ta'limotlari IX-X asrlarga mansub bo'lib islom dunyosida o'sha davrdagi ijtimoiy va ma'naviy ehtiyojlariga javob tariqasida paydo bo'lgan edi. Arablar Markaziy Osiyoni bosib olish davrida uning xalqlarini og'ir axvolga solgan edilar. «Tasavvur falsafasi sen shu ijtimoiy adolatsizlikka qarshi norozilik kayfiyati sifatida shakllandi. Bu oqim vakillarining diniy-falsafiy qarashlarida odamlar o'rtasida tobora chuqurlashib berayotgan tengsizlik va adolatsizlikni qoralash hammani o'zining kuchi bilan kun ko'rishga chiqarish g'oyalarni ilgari surildi. Tasavvur falsafasida ijtimoiy gumanistik fikrlar ustunlik qilar edi.

Kalit so'zlarlar: fikr, tasavvuf, falsafa, diniy qadriyat.

PECULIARITIES OF THE NAQSHBANDI SECT.

Abstract. Tasuvvuf emerged at the right time, inextricably linked with the formation and expansion of Islam and the process of development, and went through a long path of progress. His early teachings, dating from the 9th to the 10th centuries, had appeared in the Islamic world in response to the social and spiritual extents of the time. During the Arab conquest of Central Asia, its peoples were heavily aggrieved. "The philosophy of imagination took shape as a mood of protest against this social injustice. In the religious-philosophical views of representatives of this current, the condemnation of inequality and injustice, which is increasingly deepening among people, put forward ideas to make everyone see the day by their own power. The philosophy of imagination was dominated by social humanistic thought.

Key words: thought, mysticism, philosophy, religious value.

ОСОБЕННОСТИ СЕКТЫ НАКШБАНДИЯ.

Аннотация. Суфизм возник в свое время в связи с процессом укрепления и развития зарождения и широкого распространения ислама и прошел долгий путь развития. Его ранние учения датируются девятнадцатым и десятым веками и возникли в исламском мире в ответ на социальные и духовные потребности того времени. Арабы в период завоевания Центральной Азии поставили ее народы в тяжелое положение. "Философия воображения ты сформировался как протест против этой социальной несправедливости. В религиозно-философских воззрениях представителей этого течения выдвигались идеи осуждения все более углубляющегося неравенства и несправедливости между людьми, вывода всех на самокупаемость. В философии воображения преобладали социально-гуманистические мысли.

Ключевое слова: мысль, мистика, философия, религиозная ценность.

Hozirgi kunda dunyoda keng tarkalib borayotgan diniy mutaassiblik siyosiy muammolarni xalq etishning asosiy vositasi sifatida kuch ishlatish va zo'ravorlik qilish o'zining ijtimoiy va diniy qadriyatlarini ustun quyish g'oyalari va konsepsiyalari terrorizm hamda diniy determinizmning g'oyaviy-ma'naviy asoslarini tashkil etadi. Ularga qarshi kurashda xalqimiz ilg'or farzandlari tafakkurining mevasi bo'lishi va boy ijtimoiy falsafiy va ma'naviy

merosimizning ajralmas qismi hisoblangan tasavvur tariqatlarining xaqchil g'oyalari o'tkir qurol sifatida xizmat qila oladi¹.

Tasavvuf o'z vaqtida islom dinining vujudga kelishi va keng tarqalishi mustaxkamlanishi va rivojlanish jarayoni bilan o'zviy bog'langan holda paydo bo'ldi va uzoq taraqqiyot yo'lini bosib o'tdi. Uning ilk ta'limotlari IX-X asrlarga mansub bo'lib islom dunyosida o'sha davrdagi ijtimoiy va ma'naviy extiyolariga javob tariqasida paydo bo'lgan edi. Arablar Markaziy Osiyoni bosib olish davrida uning xalqlarini og'ir axvolga solgan edilar. «Tasavvur falsafasi sen shu ijtimoiy adolatsizlikka qarshi norozilik kayfiyati sifatida shakllandi. Bu oqim vakillarining diniy-falsafiy qarashlarida odamlar o'rtasida tobora chuqurlashib berayotgan tengsizlik va adolatsizlikni qoralash hammani o'zining kuchi bilan kun ko'rishga chiqarish g'oyalarni ilgari surildi. Tasavvur falsafasida ijtimoiy gumanistik fikrlar ustunlik qiladi».

Ammo dastlab uni siyosiy va diniy arboblardan qabul qilinishi bir xil sillik kechmadi. Ayniqsa muatassib din arboblari va ulamolari tomonidan xudosizlikda ayblangan yirik mutasavvuf olimlardan biri bo'lgan Mansur Xallol (858-932) qat qildi. Bu esa diniy ma'naviy muammolarini kuch ishlatish zo'ravonlik vositasida xal qilishning yorqin misoli edi. Extimolni shu voqea sabab tasavvu ta'limoti diniy zo'ravonlikni oldini olish unga ta'mir ko'rsatish tarzida diniy manfaatini yoqlashga yo'g'rildi. Va jamiyat shaxs ma'naviyatini axloqni mustaxkamlash uni mohiyatini senga insonparvarlashtirish inson xayotida tobora yaqinlashtirishga yo'naltirildi. Bu esa ishtiyoqlama foydali bo'ldi: dinni inson xayotiga ehtiyojiga yaqinlashtirdi va bu vazifani xal qililuvchi turli tariqatlar ko'paya bordi, ya'ni ularni xalq o'rtasiga keng tarqalishiga din peshvolari insonlik qila olmadilar. Chunki tasavvufning deyarli hamma oqimlarini birlashtiradigan tamoyillar zuxud va xudo visoliga etishish haqidagi ta'limotlardan tashqari ularning zulm va zo'ravorlikka qarshi g'oyalari xech kimga yomonlikni ravo ko'rmaslik o'zgalarga yordam berish soxiiy va sabr toqatli bo'lishi halol mehnat qilish komil inson darajasiga erishish yo'llarini ko'rsatish bilan bog'liq sa'yi-harakatlari ham tashqil etadi.

Bundan tashqari Islomning tasavvufga munosabatining o'zgarishiga nafaqat istilochilik va harbiy yurishlar bilan tarqatish mumkinligi balki xalqqa tushunarli va yoqimli bo'lgan ma'naviy axloqiy vositalar bilan keng tarqatish insoniyatining paydo bo'lganligidir. Chunki tasavvuf g'oya va ta'limotlari islomni inson kamolotiga olib boruvchi yo'l va vositalar bilan boyitdi.

Din va dindorlar uchun yana bir muhim topgani diniy g'oyalarni ortiqcha sarf harajat ijtimoiy siyosiy, iqtisodiy harbiy tadbirlarsiz tarqatish imkoniyati tug'ilganidir. Tasavvuf ilm islom ma'naviyatining qolaversa jahon taffakur olamining bu ta'limotidir. Tasavvuf maqomlari insonni donolikka donishmandlikka chorlaydi. Inson va insoniyatning donishmandligiga xizmat qiladi. Insoniyat tajribasi ko'rsatadiki, donolik mujassam bo'lganligiga ijtimoy-siyosiy iqtisodiy taraqqiyot bo'lishi mumkin.

«Tasavvuf ilmi insoniyatni idroki donishmandlik maqomi orqali insonlikka yo'naltiradi. Barcha ishlarda ilmiylik kashf etiladi. Aql-idrok orqali kishilik xuquqiga erishish o'z-o'zini erkin boshqarishga yo'llaydi» Tasavvuf yaxlit diniy axloqiy falsafiy ilmiy ta'limot hisoblandi. «Tasavvuf» ta'minotida dastlab quyidagi qoidalarga amal qiladi: «ilmiy yaqin» ya'ni mohiyatini

¹ Navro'zova G. Naqshbandiya tasavvufiy ta'limoti va barkamol inson tarbiyasi. -Toshkent: Fan, 2005 yil. –B. 12.

ilm bilan bilish; «aynul yaqin» ya'ni mohiyatini aniqlash va «xaqqul yaqin» ya'ni Alloxni bilish va uning qudratini tan olish. Bu qoidalar tasavuf ilmiga kirishning dastlabki qadamlaridir»².

Tasavvuf ta'limotini yaxlit bir fan sifatida o'rganmoq lozim. Bunda gnologik yoki metodik jihatdan bosqichma-bosqich erishiladi. Bu bosqichlar asosiy 4 ta. 1. ilm shariat. 2. ilm tariqat. 3. ilm ma'rifat. 4. ilm haqiqat. Ma'rifatda o'n yil haqiqatda o'n o'rin bilan jami va maqomni Tashqil etadi. Bulardan shariat amal qilish shart bo'lgan qonundir. Tariqat esa mujasamlashgan qat'iy odobu axloqdir. Iml ma'rifat ilm haqiqat esa avliyolarning o'zlariga xos yo'lidir. Bunda ma'rifat muridining o'zini anglab etish sari yo'l tutishi ochig'i nafsini tiyishidir. Haqiqat esa o'z ruhining tangri ruhi bilan bog'lanishiga yo'l tutishidir.

Sharqning buyuk tasavvuf mutafakkirlari Julayd Bag'dodiy, Mansur Xalloq, Muhammad G'ozzoli Yusuf Hamadoniy, Abduxoliq G'ijduvoni, Ahmad Yassaviy, Xoja Bahouddin Naqshbandlar o'zlariga yo'l tutib tasavvufni rang-barang shaklan har xil (poetik) yoki nasriy tarzda boyitganlar. Tasavvufda asosiy shaxs sufiy hisoblanadi. Sufiy uchun na dunyodan va na oxiratda ta'ma bo'lmasligi kerak. Yagona istak bu xudoning diydoridir xolos.

Mashhur so'fi ayol Robia Adviya (714-801) tangriga murojatlarida nola qilib aytar ekan; «Ey parvardigorim, ey yori aziz, agar jannatingdan benasib et agar do'zaxingdan qo'rkib ibodat qiladigan bo'lsam meni do'zax o'tida kuydir ming-ming roziman. Ammo agar sening jamolingni deb tunlarni bedor o'tkazar ekanman yolvoraman men jamolingdan maxrum etma!» Tangri taologa quruq ko'r-ko'rona muteminning xojati yuq. Xudo g'azabidan qo'rqibgina amri ma'rufni bajarish sadoqat belgisi emas, balki ziyodir. SHuning uchun sufilar: Alloxni chin dildan sevish, uning zoti va sifatlarini tanish va bilish ko'ngilni nafsu xirs g'uboridan poklab botinish musaffo bir xolatda ilon vasligi etishish va bundan lazzatlanish g'oyasini keng tartib qildilar. Inson Ruhi ilohiydir va demak asosiy maqsad-olishga borib qutilmoqdir dedilar. Shu tariqa dunyodan ko'ngil uzgan ammo zoxidlarga o'xshamaydigan zexnu zakoviy aqlu darajasida tengsiz ammo o'zga mutaffakirlar foydalanishlardan ajralib turadigan shariat ilmini suv qilib ichgan toatu ibodatda mustahkam lekin oddiy dindorlardan farqlanadigan ajoyib xislatlar odamlar toifasi paydo bo'lgan ediki, ularni Ruh kishilari deb atardilar.

Alisher Navoiy ham Bahouddin Naqshband va Abduraxmon Jomiy murshidi «ofok noshifi isrori iloh» barcha ishlardan xabardor karomatli va insoniyatli va pok niyatli zotlar sifatida ta'rif tavsif etadi. Masalan Bahouddin Naqshband.

Mulki jaxon mazmun mohiyati ul,
Balki jaxon mulki nigoxbani ul,
Yo'q manolikka nogixband bo'lib,
Barcha sanotan o'za sulton bo'lib
Xaq so'zini elga qilurda ado

Teng kurishib oldinda shoxu gado Tasavvuf ta'limoti («Xayratul Abror»dan) birdaniga emas qadam ba qadam rivojlanib nuqul diniy axloqiy talqindan ilmiy-falsafiy Ruhiy psixologik badiiy she'riy shijoatdan boyidi.

Agar IX-XI asrlarda tavxid asoslarini chuqurlashtirishga katta e'tibor berilibtasavvufning fan va baxo kabi tushunchalari xaqi visol bo'lish mayli shiddat bilan targ'ib qilingan bo'lsa XIII asr o'rtalarida boshlab tafakkuriy aqliy yo'nalsh etakchilik qila boshladi. Bu falsafiy oqim

² Komilov N. Tasavvuf yoki komil inson axloqi. Birinchi kitob. -Toshkent, 1996 yil. –B. 47.

tasavvuf tarixida «vakdjagud vujud» nomi bilan shuxrat topdi. Sufilar endi tuzilishi odamlarning xususiyatlari olam va odam munosabatlari nomi inson anglamalari bilan bosh qotiradigan bo'ldilar. Natijada ibn Arabiy va Jaloliddin Rumiy kabi zotlarning asarlarida butun bir falsafiy tizim o'z ifodasini topdi, ular ilohiy nashr karomat Ruhiiy psixologik xolatlar latifalar bilan birga real insoniy hayot haqida ham shunda ko'p ijobiy fikrlarni bayon etdilar. Shunday qilib, tasavvuf sharq fikriy taraqqiyotidagi ko'p asrlik tajribalarni o'z ichiga qamrab olib, uni rivojlantirdi din va falsafa tinmay va vaxdiy kalom va hadis ilmlarini birlashtirdi ilohiy ilmlar bilan dunyoviy ilmlarni o'zaro bog'lashga harakat qildi. Natijada tasavvuf sharq kishisining tafakkur to'zi va axloq normasini belgilaydigan xodisasiga aylanib qoldi.

IX asr boshlariga kelib tasavvufning nazariy asoslari ishlab chiqildi, sufilarning amaliy Ruhiiy psixologik mashqlari o'z-o'zini tarbiyalash va chiniqtirish tadbir usullari shakllandi³.

Mavloni dedi: bu so'zlarning ma'nosini hamma bilishi lozim emas. Agar hamma xudoning yagonaligiga iqroridir va xudoning xoliku roziq jonini tan oladilar... Shuning uchun bu so'zlarni eshitgach va ushbu so'zlar xaqning va siri va zikridir, bas ular hammaning qalbini titratdi, va zavq nasil qildi. Chunki bu so'zlardan Ma'shukning xidi va ularning matlabi namoyon edi. Yo'llar xilma-xil bo'lsa ham, lekin maqsad birdir. Karachin Ka'baga olib boradigan yo'llar ko'p. Birovlar rumdan, birovlar Shomu ajaldan yo'lga chiqadilar» yo'llar turlicha maqsad bir Ka'baga borib poklanish hammani birlashtiradi.

Tasavvufda ibratli xislat - o'z-o'ziga murosasiz bo'lmoq. Shumlik va gunoxlarni bekitmok xiyonat hisoblanadi. Inson poklanish uchun o'z nafi bilan ayovsiz va botiniy kurash olib boradi. O'z gunohlariga mardona nazar tashlaydi. Gunohni anglash gunoh qilmaslikning chorasidir. Gunohlik tuyg'usiga tobelik-poklanish istagiga erk berish ichki nido unga tinchlik bermaydi. Bu ovoz yolg'izligi bilan diqqatni chuqur jalb qiladi va qalbda o'z -o'zining bilan qolish o'zligini tekshirish istiroblarni qo'zg'aydi. U inson umrining harakat tarzini juda nozik ilg'aydi. Tasavvufda IX asrda malomatiya mazhabi yuzaga kelgan bo'lib, uning markazi Nishopur bo'lgan malotiya mashabiga mansub kishilar uchun o'z-o'zini komillashtirish yurakni poklash bosh vazifa hisoblanganligini yozadi.

Ammo bu ish mutlaqo shaxsiy harakat tarzida atrofdagilardan yashirin ko'z - ko'z qilinmasdan oshirilishi shart bo'lgan. «Sodda qilib aytganda malotiya - bu insonning o'z-o'zini taxlildan o'tkazish, taxlil etgan sayin qusuri nuqsonlar uchun o'zini ayamalik va ularni malomat tilida fosh qilmoq yo'lidir»⁴ Bu yo'lga kirgan inson barcha yomon xislatlarini sira yashirmasdan oshkor qilib yaxshi fazilatlarini esa qat'iyat bilan ponxon saqlagan shu zaylda o'zini axloqiy jihatdan takomillashtirgan. Mumtoz merosimizda Ahmad Yassaviy malomatiya mazxabining yorqin namoyondasi va badiiy ifodachisi edi. U o'zining xikmatlarida malomatiya qonun qoidalari asosida fikr yuritib odamni o'z o'ziga tanqidiy nazar bilan qarashga da'vat qiladi. Har qanday din kabi islom dini ham insonning bosar tusarini bilmay yashab, gunox qilishin qoralaydi. Ammo gunohlariga iqrorlikni to'la yo'qlaydi. Chunki tovba tazarrutozalanish poklanish demakdir. SHuni alohida ta'kidlash lozimki gunohkorlik faqat aybdorligiga iqrorlik emas eng muhimi uning mohiyatini sababini tushunish va undan qaytish. «Haqiqatning muqaddas eshigiga kalit solish hamdir». Xoja Ahmad YAssaviyasoslagan

³ Buxoriy Xoji Abdulg'afur Razoq. Tariqatga yo'llanma (Naqshbandiya ta'limoti asosidir). - Toshkent: Movarounnahr, 2003 yil. -B. 25.

⁴ Abul Muxsin Muhammad Bokir ibn Muhammad Ali Bahouddin Balogardon. - Toshkent: Yozuvchi, 1993 yil. -B.

Yassaviya tariqati markazida pokiza ilohiy ishq yotadi. Bu ishq insonni dunyoviy illatlardan xalos qilib, kalbi nur bo'lik kirib, insonni olloh vasligi xidoyat etadigan qudrat, ma'rifat va haqiqatga eltuvchi, kishini o'zligini anglash, insoniylik mohiyatini kashf qiluvchi vosita hisoblanadi.

Yassaviya tariqatida «ishq ham dard va ham darmon, ham azob va ham roxat. Tariqatning barcha masalalari - xoll va fano, botin va zoxin, xayrat va tavxiti, bexudlik va devonalik va xokazolar ishq tushunchasi orqali anglashiladi va tushuniriladi. Yassaviya talqinida ilohiy ishq mohiyatini anglamagan odam tasavurni tushunmaydi. Uning talablari, u yo'lga kirgan kishi uning aqida va g'oyalari to'la idrok eta olmaydi. Yassaviy ijodidagi uzlat, sadoqat va mexr shavkat g'oyalari yayniy shu ishqg'oyasi bilan uyg'un bo'lib, ularni bir-biridan alohida tasavvur qilish mumkin emas. Ko'nglida pok ishqbor odam doimo poklik va uning timsoli bo'lgan ollohga intiladi. Yassaviy ta'sirida ishq faqat ilohni sevish, unga sig'inib ox nola qilish emas balki uni tanish, o'zini bilish va kamolot yo'lidir. Axmad Yassaviy Markaziy Osiyo tasavvuf shayxlari ichida turkiy tilda she'riy tarzda o'z sufiyona ta'limotini bayon qilgan mutafakkir hisoblanadi. O'z she'riyatida islomiy haqiqatlarni va tasavvuf ta'limotini yuksak maxorat bilan omuxta etib shariatni bir butun deb bilib iymon va sadoqat g'oyalari qizg'in extiros ila kuylagan».

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